

Best Predictor for Fiber - Yarn Relationship using Hybrid Neuro - Fuzzy Logic

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Abstract:

A crucial process in the textile industry is spinning. There is a distinct relationship between the provided fibers and the yarn that is created during the process of spinning. The relationship between the input and output quality is not linear. Several approaches, such as the Artificial Neural Network framework and multiple regressions method, were used in an attempt to establish the aforementioned relationship. This study uses Hybrid Neuro Fuzzy Logic (HNFL) to anticipate multi-property fibers based on yarn characteristics. This work describes the development of an ANFIS-based yarn-quality forecasting system that can predict five qualities of cotton yarns by entering nine fiber parameters into the framework. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that the predictive model performed well in accurately forecasting yarn qualities with a relative error of less than 0.00356266 percent. The outcomes reveal that the Takasi Sugeno Kang Fuzzy Inference System based ANFIS model produces more precise and reliable predictions. The proposed model serves as an excellent foundation for the creation of comparable applications designed for intricate models that need prediction and multi-objective optimization.

Keywords: Artificial Neural Network, ANFIS, Hybrid Neuro-Fuzzy Logic, Predictions, Takasi Sugeno Kang fuzzy Inference System

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1. Introduction

Yarn quality is significantly influenced by fiber characteristics, spinning technique, spinning equipment, mill temperature and humidity, and other variables. The most crucial of these variables for yarn quality is fiber properties. The quality of any cotton yarn is primarily determined by fiber qualities such as strength (STR), yellowness (+B), span length (SL), micronaire (MIC), degrees of reflectance (RD), color grade (CG), trash (TR), short fiber index (SFI), and uniformity index (UNF). As a result, choosing the right cotton is critical for producing a high-quality yarn. Yarn quality is measured by features such as coefficient of mass variation (CV %), count strength product (CSP), twists per inch (TIP), irregularity (U %), thinness (-50%), thickness (+50%), neps (+280%), imperfection index (TOTAL IPI), hair, and elongation. Several models have been devised by researchers to ascertain the relationship between fiber and yarn. The multiple regression approach, which calculates coefficients that are frequently only applicable to a given population and operating circumstances, is the main component of the statistical methodology. The empirical method makes the unfounded assumption that yarn qualities are only influenced by fiber characteristics, which is not necessarily the case [1, 2]. By using the neural network, yarn characteristics may be predicted based on fiber properties. There is no universal Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model since various sectors use different metrics for predicting yarn characteristics. All spinners aren't going to use an identical set of input qualities to produce the desired yarn. Span length, tenacity, the fiber quality index (FQI), and so on are a few examples. As a result, the ANN architecture varies for each spinner [3-7].

Two forms of artificial intelligence, ANN and fuzzy systems, are becoming more well-known in the field of learning. This is mostly because to their innate parallelism, their capacity for learning and adaptation, and, to a lesser extent, their improved error tolerance. As mentioned above, fuzzy logic and neural networks offer numerous benefits. However, one disadvantage of fuzzy control is that, once control laws and membership functions are created, they must be updated whenever a new kind of system arises. A further drawback of the neural network is

that it takes a long time to train as many neurons as the system's complexity, and during the learning process it is prone to focusing on the local minimum instead of the global minimum. Research on HNFL, the fusion of neural networks with fuzzy logic, is underway in an effort to compensate for the flaws. A proposed HNFL system combines qualitative knowledge of symbolic fuzzy rules and neural networks' capacity for learning. ANFIS integrates the advantages of ANN and fuzzy systems. The ANFIS generates input-output linkages and may serve as a basis for fuzzy rules with appropriate membership functions. With proper training, the produced fuzzy inference system (FIS) can predict every spun yarn.

2. Selection of Yarn Parameters

Selecting the appropriate yarn properties is essential in different spinning technology. The quality of the fiber determines the quality of yarn spun from cotton. The choice of yarn parameters is essential to guaranteeing the effectiveness, durability, and affordability of textile products. Selected characteristics are in accordance with the production process, client preferences, and the functional needs of the final product. Studies are conducted using artificial intelligence methods like neural networks, fuzzy logic, and their hybrid combinations, using the vast amounts of data that are accessible from a reputable spinning companies. The potential to lower costs by offering the chance to replace more costly cotton in blending without compromising quality or processing efficiency is what gives blending its economic impact. It's critical that yarn parameters remain consistent. In this paper we use the important yarn parameters which are used to define the quality of yarn are CV%, CSP, TPI, Total IPI, hairiness and elongations.

3. ANFIS Predictor Modelization

An ANFIS is a kind of adaptive network Fig. 1 that consists of many layers with a feed-forward architecture. In ANFIS, each node has a specific node function, which it applies to incoming signals. In addition, each node has a set of parameters connected with it. The intended input–output mapping is attained by updating these parameters in accordance with the provided hybrid learning rule and data. The hybrid learning method involves two iterations: one in the forward direction and one in the backward direction. In the forward pass, the input information undergoes functional transformations and advances to the output layer 5, where parameters are found using the least square equation and the error measure is computed. The gradient approach is used in the backward pass to adjust the layer 1 parameters as the error rates travel from the output side towards the input end [8].

3.1 Elements of ANFIS Architecture

Fig. 1 illustrates the architecture of the ANFIS, with square nodes representing functions requiring parameter learning and circular nodes representing fixed operations.

Figure 1: Architecture of ANFIS

Let \$m\$ and \$n\$ be two inputs that construct two fuzzy rules.

Rule No 1: If \$m\$ is \$A_1\$ and \$n\$ is \$B_1\$, then \$f_1 = a_1m + b_1n + c_1\$;

Rule No 2: If \$m\$ is \$A_2\$ and \$n\$ is \$B_2\$, then \$f_2 = a_2m + b_2n + c_2\$ (1)

The fuzzy rule's premise variables are represented by the inputs \$m\$ and \$n\$. The premise parameters are indicated by \$A_1\$ and \$B_1\$. \$a_1\$, \$b_1\$, and \$c_1\$ make up the consequences parameter. Equation (2) uses the weight values of \$w_1\$ and \$w_2\$, the \$f_1\$ and \$f_2\$ functions, and the total output function \$F\$.

$$O = \frac{w_1 f_1 + w_2 f_2}{w_1 + w_2} = \bar{w}_1 f_1 + \bar{w}_2 f_2 \quad (2)$$

With reference to Fig. 1 five layers are present in the ANFIS architecture [9].

Layer No. 1: All nodes in this layer are adaptable. Here the fuzzification process occurs. Outputs are the membership values of the premise portion. The output of each node is represented by equation (3).

$$\begin{aligned} Out_{1,i} &= \mu_{A_i}(m) \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2 \\ Out_{1,i} &= \mu_{B_{i-2}}(m) \quad \text{for } i = 3, 4 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

For inputs m and n , the membership grade is thus $Out_{1,i}(m)$. Any shape, including bell, trapezoidal, triangular, and others, might be used for the membership purposes. The function with a triangular form is provided by

$$Tri_i(m) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } m \leq x_i \\ \frac{m - x_i}{y_i - x_i} = \frac{1}{y_i - x_i} m - \frac{x_i}{y_i - x_i} & \text{if } x_i \leq m \leq y_i \\ \frac{z_i - m}{z_i - y_i} = \frac{-1}{z_i - y_i} m + \frac{z_i}{z_i - y_i} & \text{if } y_i \leq m \leq z_i \\ 0 & \text{if } z_i \leq m \end{cases}$$

Layer No.2: Equation (4), which represents the weight of the rule, determines the output of each fixed node in this layer.

$$Out_{2,i} = w_i = \mu_{A_i}(m)\mu_{B_i}(n) \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2 \quad (4)$$

Layer No. 3: Once again, the nodes in this layer are fixed. Equation (5) gives the calculated ratio of the firing weight of the i^{th} rule to the total weights of all the rules.

$$Out_{3,i} = \bar{w}_i = \frac{w_i}{w_1 + w_2} \quad (5)$$

Layer No.4: The nodes work as a function block, with adaptive parameters and variables representing input values. Equation (6) Produces TSK outputs.

$$Out_{4,i} = \bar{w}_i f_i = \bar{w}_i (a_i x + b_i y + c_i) \quad (6)$$

Here the resultant parameters that need to be found are a_i , b_i , and c_i .

Layer No.5: The sum of all incoming signals is this layer's output. Equation (7) represents the whole output.

$$Out_{5,i} = \sum_i \bar{w}_i f_i = \frac{\sum_i w_i f_i}{\sum_i w_i} \quad (7)$$

To map the input-output dataset, the ANFIS associates the parameters with a specific membership function. Fig. 1 shows that the Takagi-Sugeno model's output membership functions are linear but its input membership functions are non-linear. In order to optimize the parameters based on an input-output dataset, the hybrid learning algorithm which incorporates the error back-propagation technique with the least squares method, is the most efficient approach. The error back propagation technique is an appropriate optimization procedure as the input functions are non-linear. Since the output functions are linear, the least squares estimate approach works very well.

In summary, the advantages of the ANFIS algorithm over the ANN model lie in its fuzzy logic-based paradigm, which leverages the ANN's learning capabilities to improve the performance of intelligent systems by using past information. The ANFIS builds a FIS from a given input-output dataset, and then uses the least squares approach together with the back-propagation technique to tune (change) the membership function parameters. By using these strategies, the fuzzy modelling process may acquire knowledge about the dataset and use that knowledge to calculate the membership function parameters that will enable the associated FIS to monitor the input-output data most effectively. An input layer, hidden layers, and an output layer make up the structure of the ANN model. These layers have fixed nodes, and the error back-propagation approach is employed to alter the synaptic weights. Since there are two methods of learning in the ANFIS—gradient descent is used employed for backward learning and the least square estimate technique is used employed for forward learning—it is clear that flexibility in parameters is related to nodes and that this will improve non-linear mapping. The ANFIS has a quick convergence rate and

requires minimal training data. Here, we provide an ANFIS-based modelling approach that leverages the neural network at the front end to maximize system efficiency while preserving all the benefits of fuzzy systems.

3.2 Training ANFIS Predictor

Matlab's Neuro-Fuzzy toolbox was used to train the ANFIS predictor. An input-output data set is used by the ANFIS to construct a TSKFIS. It enables the fuzzy system to acquire knowledge from the modelled system's data collection. Gradient vector ensures membership parameter calculation.

4. Result and Discussion

For the purpose of this research, various cotton varieties were selected to encompass all staple length categories of cotton cultivated in India. A grand total of 20 cottons varieties were examined H1098, RS 875, NHH 44, F 846BRAHMA, LH 1556, J34, PHULE 492, G Cot 16, DHH11,G Cot HY 10, F414, MCU 5, DCH 32, Shankar-4, BUNNY, Shankar-6, Gujarat -17, Hybrid 4and H777 were among the varieties that were examined. After conditioning the cottons for moisture equilibrium, they were evaluated in a controlled environment of 64.9% relative humidity with a temperature maintained at 27.5°C using a High Volume Instrument. The HVI system measures SL, SFI, MIC, STR, TR, RD, +B, CG, and UNF.

For the experiment, the average values of the fiber qualities were taken into account. The fiber length range that was examined ranged from 21.8 to 30.5 mm. The BRAHMA variety of cotton has the lowest SL of all the varieties under study, measuring 21.8 mm. The greatest fiber length measured for MCU 5 was determined to be 30.5 mm. RS. 875 have the lowest MIC value. In this investigation, it was discovered that NHH 44 and Phule 492 contained the lowest SFI. DCH32 revealed the least TR values, whereas BUNNY showed the highest. The results also showed that F 414 had the highest elongation value of 6.7%, while LH 1556 had the least amount of elongation of 6.4%. We analyzed the yarn samples for CV %, CSP, TIP, TOTAL IPI, Hair and Elongation.

There are 300 distinct textile industry samples in this collection, representing 20 distinct kinds. Two groups were created using the information that was gathered from the spinning industry. Two sets were utilized: one for testing and the other for learning. There are 250 samples in the training dataset and 50 samples in the testing dataset. The ANFIS block needs to learn from the dataset, as Fig. 1 illustrates. Six inputs and one output make up the used ANFIS. By changing the kind, quantity, and structure of the input membership functions as well as the output membership function type, several strategies were examined. Table 1 provides a full summary of the learning phase's outcomes.

Table 1: Results of the Learning Phase

Input Membership		Training Method	Output Membership	Error CV%	Error CSP	Error TPI	Error Total IPI	Error Hair	Error Elongation	Epoch
Type	No.									
Triangle	2	Hybrid	Const	36.2217	0.044018	4.1764	38.1145	0.37626	0.14577	50
			Linear	0.26066	0.00019477	0.011818	0.069013	0.00062476	0.00073541	50
		BP	Const	86.8244	1.1645	23.9382	109.2304	4.3031	5.1567	50
			Linear	75.4152	0.07682	11.8228	97.6133	0.39703	0.16792	50
	3	Hybrid	Const	0.0010304	1.2265×10^{-05}	0.00036745	0.0041306	4.0193×10^{-05}	3.67×10^{-05}	50
			Linear	4.241×10^{-05}	4.8064×10^{-07}	6.8422×10^{-06}	4.3752×10^{-05}	1.3486×10^{-06}	1.99×10^{-06}	50
BP	Const	86.8754	1.2189	23.9921	109.2813	4.3575	5.2109	50		
	Linear	2.3588	0.041313	16.6874	102.3448	0.33725	0.3942	50		
Trapeze	2	Hybrid	Const	34.8789	0.041999	4.0566	33.38	0.35483	0.13477	50
			Linear	0.0026274	3.5261×10^{-06}	0.00036354	0.0028844	3.0673×10^{-05}	1.99×10^{-05}	50
		BP	Const	86.8158	1.1544	23.9278	109.225	4.2933	5.146	50
			Linear	74.7952	0.097391	11.2462	97.173	0.37711	0.17766	50
	3	Hybrid	Const	0.00081286	7.2951×10^{-06}	0.00015019	0.00047274	2.9781×10^{-05}	5.51×10^{-05}	50
			Linear	4.5452×10^{-05}	6.6042×10^{-07}	1.2718×10^{-05}	6.1163×10^{-05}	2.266×10^{-06}	2.76×10^{-06}	50
BP	Const	86.8775	1.2274	24.0001	109.2873	4.3654	5.2213	50		
	Linear	80.1874	0.047503	17.5214	102.8822	0.30294	0.32522	50		
Bell	2	Hybrid	Const	34.3232	0.041469	3.968	34.66	0.35432	0.13842	50
			Linear	0.016278	1.5452×10^{-05}	0.0017723	0.013597	0.00011152	8.21×10^{-05}	50
		BP	Const	86.8092	1.143	23.9174	109.2122	4.2817	5.1352	50
			Linear	74.0619	0.076506	9.9794	95.9465	0.39035	0.18495	50

Gauss	3	Hybrid	Const	0.0022973	1.2324×10^{-05}	0.00033941	0.0031114	3.7278×10^{-05}	3.73×10^{-05}	50
			Linear	0.00020619	2.7601×10^{-06}	4.4254×10^{-05}	0.00023797	9.7336×10^{-05}	1.1×10^{-05}	50
	BP	Const	86.8293	1.1667	23.9392	109.237	4.3054	5.2902	50	
		Linear	75.979	0.055151	12.5297	98.3459	0.33113	0.22165	50	
	2	Hybrid	Const	34.4908	0.042466	4.0232	34.8579	0.37134	0.1397	50
			Linear	0.022138	3.0658×10^{-05}	0.0041324	0.025864	0.00025913	0.00017538	50
BP	Const	86.8077	1.1413	23.9159	109.2107	4.2799	5.1335	50		
	Linear	73.9251	0.075801	9.8428	95.8102	0.39893	0.18134	50		
3	Hybrid	Const	0.002426	1.2784×10^{-05}	0.00032939	0.0036689	4.4209×10^{-05}	3.84×10^{-05}	50	
		Linear	0.00012438	1.2567×10^{-06}	3.2232×10^{-05}	0.00012522	5.3798×10^{-06}	7.21×10^{-06}	50	
	BP	Const	86.8012	1.1382	23.9114	109.2127	4.2767	5.1297	50	
		Linear	73.5191	0.063827	10.5355	96.166	0.37247	0.22308	50	
Gauss2	2	Hybrid	Const	36.7239	0.042978	4.0353	33.2257	0.34241	0.14024	50
			Linear	0.064929	4.9543×10^{-06}	0.00036309	0.0039281	3.3329×10^{-05}	2.50×10^{-05}	50
	BP	Const	86.8072	1.1432	23.917	109.2104	4.2804	5.1348	50	
		Linear	73.9274	0.094745	10.3764	95.7571	0.40339	0.17989	50	
	3	Hybrid	Const	0.0010779	8.5547×10^{-06}	0.00016299	0.0012288	2.9542×10^{-05}	5.69×10^{-05}	50
			Linear	0.00018244	2.8895×10^{-06}	5.9483×10^{-05}	0.0002546	1.3274×10^{-05}	1.22×10^{-05}	50
BP	Const	86.8731	1.1898	23.9814	109.0131	4.3259	5.1799	50		
	Linear	79.9767	0.053063	16.1161	104.165	0.3039	0.33992	50		
Pi	2	Hybrid	Const	38.4341	0.042209	4.043	34.0061	0.34317	0.13608	50
			Linear	0.71628	4.1089×10^{-06}	0.00026401	0.0023974	2.1237×10^{-05}	1.31×10^{-05}	50
	BP	Const	86.815	1.1571	23.9319	109.2268	4.2957	5.1494	50	
		Linear	74.5964	0.097422	11.605	97.3184	0.384	0.18513	50	
	3	Hybrid	Const	0.071121	7.9074×10^{-05}	0.00015105	0.00077832	2.7953×10^{-05}	8.69×10^{-05}	50
			Linear	6.3544×10^{-5}	9.8685×10^{-07}	1.7826×10^{-05}	9.2547×10^{-05}	3.2252×10^{-06}	4.03×10^{-06}	50
BP	Const	86.8733	1.2251	23.9963	109.2832	4.363	5.217	50		
	Linear	79.8096	0.063557	17.155	102.4882	0.22385	0.13615	50		
Psi	2	Hybrid	Const	33.4995	0.041545	4.0431	33.2041	0.34045	0.13675	50
			Linear	0.0034485	4.9162×10^{-05}	0.00031777	0.0030707	2.6504×10^{-05}	2.32×10^{-05}	50
	BP	Const	86.8087	1.1474	23.9219	109.2208	4.2861	5.1396	50	
		Linear	74.0274	0.097111	10.6752	96.8228	0.38617	0.1712	50	
	3	Hybrid	Const	0.001005	1.0525×10^{-05}	0.00019513	0.0010337	3.2379×10^{-05}	6.01×10^{-05}	50
			Linear	0.001655	4.2761×10^{-06}	8.5219×10^{-05}	0.00045455	1.5042×10^{-05}	1.73×10^{-05}	50
BP	Const	4.5366	1.2158	23.9905	109.2868	4.3542	5.2078	50		
	Linear	7907822	0.058971	17.0124	102.3828	0.28348	0.26744	50		
Dsig	2	Hybrid	Const	33.4995	0.041545	4.0431	33.204	0.34045	0.13675	50
			Linear	0.003421	5.5833×10^{-06}	0.0003109	0.0030844	2.6392×10^{-05}	1.85×10^{-05}	50
	BP	Const	86.8087	1.1474	23.9219	109.2208	4.2861	5.1396	50	
		Linear	74.0274	0.097111	10.6752	96.8228	0.38617	0.1712	50	
	3	Hybrid	Const	0.001005	1.0525×10^{-05}	0.00019513	0.0010337	3.2379×10^{-05}	6.01×10^{-05}	50
			Linear	0.00032278	4.2568×10^{-06}	8.4107×10^{-05}	0.00046465	1.5078×10^{-05}	1.73×10^{-05}	50
BP	Const	86.8719	1.2158	23.9905	109.2868	4.3542	5.2078	50		
	Linear	79.7821	0.058971	17.0123	102.2857	0.28339	0.26744	50		

After both systems were trained, an evaluation was conducted on the remaining 100 samples. Qualities of the projected yarn were CV %, CSP, TIP, TOTAL IPI, hair and Elongation. Training aims to accurately generalize the correlation between input and output datasets. Based on a review of the facts in Table 1, the strategy indicated in input membership type-triangle, number-3, training method-hybrid and output membership type-linear should be selected for the most accurate prediction.

5. Conclusion

To anticipate yarn quality, it is necessary to predict yarn quality more accurately throughout the spinning process. In this article, a best predictor for fiber - yarn relationship was evaluated using Hybrid Neuro - Fuzzy Logic, to predict six yarn properties such as CV %, CSP, TIP, TOTAL IPI, Hair and Elongation. Accuracy can satisfy the demands of spinning factories, therefore anticipating outcomes would be valuable for directing spinning practice.

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